

Detecting and Investigating Polytomous Items with Nonuniform-bidirectional Drift

Abstract:

The Monte Carlo simulation was employed to model two testing administrations, encompassing 81 scenarios, where polytomous items demonstrated nonuniform-bidirectional drift. The findings revealed notable impacts of the drift on distinct ability groups and substantiated the efficacy of the Weighted Root Mean Square Difference in identifying nonuniform-bidirectional drift over conventional methods.

Item parameter drift (IPD) is typically considered when items from successive testing administrations do not remain invariant due to factors other than sampling error (Goldstein, 1983). Some researchers have investigated the factors that cause IPD and how to detect the drift (see Bock et al., 1988; Mislevy, 1982; DeMars, 2004; Donoghue & Isham, 1998; Han, 2008). However, they have focused primarily on dichotomously scored items and few have examined the influence of drifted polytomous items (Li, 2012; Wang & Hambleton, 2014). With the rise of using items with multiple score points in Computer-Based Testing (CBT), this underscores the urgent need for research into how polytomous items IPD affects ability estimates to uphold test fairness and score interpretation validity.

One observed gap in the literature is the exclusive study of a uniform drift pattern in polytomous IPD research, where item parameters drift in a consistent and comparable manner. This oversimplification overlooks the plausible scenario of nonuniform-bidirectional drift patterns, where item parameters vary in direction and magnitude. For example, imagine a 3-point item whose threshold parameters are (-1.25, 0.5, 1.25), the uniform-unidirectional drift pattern with a drift of 0.2 would result in parameters (-1.25+0.2, 0.5+0.2, 1.25+0.2). However, the nonuniform-bidirectional drift pattern could result in a situation where parameter change more drastically, for example: (-1.25-0.5, 0.5+0.2, 1.25+0.3).

The nonuniform-bidirectional pattern is much more often seen in actual testing situations (See Mislevy (1982)). An important open question is that such a drift pattern is very likely to remain undetected using the well-acceptable identification criteria using a global difficulty change. The global difficulty change is based on the average value of all the threshold changes. For example, a three point polytomous items with an average absolute drift amount greater than 0.155 is identified as IPD (see Raju, 1999; Meade, Lautenschlager, & Johnson, 2007). Obviously, the prior nonuniform-bidirectional drift pattern example with parameter drift of (-1.25-0.5, 0.5+0.2, 1.25+0.3) would not be flagged as IPD because the global difficulty change is 0, but notice the separation between thresholds is expanding as the effect of thresholds becoming both easier and harder with the bidirectionality along with nonuniform magnitude changes.

Given these considerations, the pivotal question of this research is: How does the undetected nonuniform-bidirectional drift pattern influence the assessment of candidates' abilities? Since weighted root mean squared difference (WRMSD) has been seen in determining if an drifted item needs to be removed (Li, 2012), this study also investigated the extent to which WRMSD can identify IPD that went undetected when using global difficulty change.¹

¹ The WRMSD can be calculated by taking the square root of NCDIF index (Raju et al, 1995), which is used to estimate the magnitude of item-level Differential Item Functioning (DIF). Note Raju (1999) recommended 0.024 as the cut-off

A Monte Carlo simulation study was done with a 3 (drifted pattern = decay exponential function, opposite, extreme) \times 3 (WRMSD magnitude = 0.1, 0.15, 0.2) \times 3 (ratios of number of dichotomous items to number of polytomous items = 25:75, 50:50, 75:25) \times 3 (proportion of items exhibiting IPD = 15%, 22%, 34%). Table 1 summarizes the simulated drift patterns under different WRMSD magnitudes.

For each replication, the first administration (prior drift) used the Rasch and partial credit model (Masters, 1982) to generate dichotomous items and polytomous items respectively. In the second administration, the corresponding proportion of polytomous items' locations drifted with the three patterns. For this research, the MC item locations are maintained to isolate the effects of the polytomous drift. In total of 1,000 candidates were randomly sampled from a normal distribution ($N \sim (0,1)$) within the interval (-2.5, 2.5). The average bias and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) were calculated under each simulated condition. Due to the brevity of the submission guidelines, only brief results can be presented at this time. All of the simulations have been completed and analyzed, and would be available for presentation.

Results of exponential decay drift pattern under all simulation conditions are presented in Table 2-4. In general, larger positive differences were observed at the lower end of the ability, and such difference approached trivial nonmeaningful differences as ability approaches to the value of middle threshold, and then become more negative. The results show that the average differences increase when there are more IPD items. Given the drift items proportion, the longer exam results in larger bias.

In a quick summary, this study informs the importance of using the step difficulty to detect the potential IPD item, by showing the varying effect of the nonuniform-bidirectional drift pattern on abilities estimates. Also, the positive correlation between WRMSD and bias magnitude provides support for using WRMSD to detect polytomous items IPD.

Table 1
A summary of simulated drift pattern and IPD magnitude:

Drift Pattern	Magnitude of item parameter drift (WRMSD)		
	0.1	0.15	0.2
Decay exponential function	$a = -0.4 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times A}$ $b = -0.4 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times B}$ $c = -0.4 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times C}$	$a = -0.5 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times A}$ $b = -0.5 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times B}$ $c = -0.5 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times C}$	$a = -0.7 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times A}$ $b = -0.7 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times B}$ $c = -0.7 \times 0.45^{1.2 \times C}$
Opposite	a=-0.4, b=-0.2, c=0.6	a=-0.5, b=-0.3, c=0.8	a=-0.7, b=-0.4, c=1.1
Extreme	a=-0.5, b=0, c=0.5	a=-0.7, b=0, c=0.7	a=-0.9, b=0, c=0.9

value for polytomous item with three response options, but Li (2012) used 0.15 ($\sqrt{0.024}$) as a criterion for IPD detection for polytomous items with three or four response options.

Table 2.
Theta Bias for 25 Dichotomous and 75 Polytomous Items with exponential decay drift pattern

No. of Drifted Items	Drift Magnitude	Ability									
		(-2.5, -2)	(-2,-1.5)	(-1.5,-1)	(-1,-0.5)	(-0.5,0)	(0,0.5)	(0.5,1)	(1,1.5)	(1.5,2)	(2, 2.5)
11	low	0.084	0.073	0.049	0.035	0.009	-0.006	-0.027	-0.038	-0.064	-0.067
	middle	0.126	0.072	0.074	0.046	0.021	-0.011	-0.032	-0.041	-0.062	-0.067
	large	0.173	0.114	0.084	0.047	0.006	-0.026	-0.057	-0.077	-0.115	-0.125
17	low	0.144	0.087	0.073	0.048	0.017	-0.018	-0.043	-0.054	-0.077	-0.100
	middle	0.162	0.140	0.104	0.063	0.027	-0.013	-0.042	-0.064	-0.083	-0.098
	large	0.226	0.163	0.111	0.065	0.015	-0.039	-0.084	-0.112	-0.156	-0.188
26	low	0.230	0.160	0.129	0.074	0.029	-0.024	-0.063	-0.102	-0.138	-0.165
	middle	0.292	0.229	0.178	0.102	0.041	-0.018	-0.069	-0.118	-0.156	-0.196
	large	0.381	0.281	0.191	0.106	0.022	-0.059	-0.130	-0.203	-0.258	-0.319

Table 3.
Theta Bias for 50 Dichotomous and 50 Polytomous Items with exponential decay drift pattern

No. of Drifted Items	Drift Magnitude	Ability									
		(-2.5, -2)	(-2,-1.5)	(-1.5,-1)	(-1,-0.5)	(-0.5,0)	(0,0.5)	(0.5,1)	(1,1.5)	(1.5,2)	(2, 2.5)
8	low	0.031	0.049	0.042	0.026	0.011	-0.015	-0.020	-0.038	-0.045	-0.037
	middle	0.078	0.078	0.067	0.032	0.019	-0.010	-0.019	-0.041	-0.063	-0.043
	large	0.096	0.107	0.070	0.038	0.011	-0.026	-0.048	-0.071	-0.101	-0.112
11	low	0.091	0.090	0.067	0.035	0.016	-0.005	-0.025	-0.052	-0.069	-0.088
	middle	0.143	0.110	0.083	0.056	0.026	-0.011	-0.032	-0.060	-0.081	-0.114
	large	0.189	0.148	0.103	0.056	0.018	-0.031	-0.066	-0.093	-0.144	-0.166
17	low	0.180	0.146	0.119	0.066	0.018	-0.014	-0.052	-0.085	-0.115	-0.110
	middle	0.227	0.189	0.140	0.089	0.038	-0.007	-0.054	-0.100	-0.114	-0.137
	large	0.306	0.243	0.165	0.093	0.025	-0.043	-0.110	-0.164	-0.214	-0.264

Table 4.
Theta Bias for 75 Dichotomous and 25 Polytomous Items with exponential decay drift pattern

No. of Drifted Items	Drift Magnitude	Ability									
		(-2.5, -2)	(-2,-1.5)	(-1.5,-1)	(-1,-0.5)	(-0.5,0)	(0,0.5)	(0.5,1)	(1,1.5)	(1.5,2)	(2, 2.5)
4	low	0.045	0.042	0.008	0.019	0.007	-0.002	-0.017	-0.019	-0.033	-0.020
	middle	0.057	0.051	0.022	0.031	0.012	-0.002	-0.015	-0.030	-0.033	-0.037
	large	0.080	0.066	0.026	0.029	0.009	-0.015	-0.034	-0.052	-0.051	-0.050
6	low	0.072	0.065	0.047	0.028	0.010	-0.010	-0.021	-0.036	-0.043	-0.042
	middle	0.084	0.087	0.067	0.043	0.016	-0.004	-0.020	-0.042	-0.051	-0.049
	large	0.115	0.121	0.070	0.039	0.007	-0.024	-0.046	-0.073	-0.088	-0.079
9	low	0.088	0.077	0.062	0.034	0.016	-0.013	-0.033	-0.056	-0.058	-0.061
	middle	0.127	0.110	0.088	0.047	0.031	-0.009	-0.030	-0.062	-0.070	-0.079
	large	0.174	0.134	0.098	0.054	0.021	-0.026	-0.069	-0.107	-0.125	-0.134

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